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Abstract : *In our country present in the day language to study has been attention from the day to the day increased is going In particular before school education , school , higher and medium special education in institutions one how much foreign languages as a science being taught is coming . In this process study with many problems surface will come Especially at school young language learner students between row this such as problems meeting can This in the article school age children language learning during precisely in reading and teaching some disadvantages and their solutions regarding thought held .*

Key words : *Phonetics difficulties , visual aids , teaching qualification , grammar structures .*

MAKTAB YOSHIDAGI BOLALARNI READING O'QITISHDAGI MUAMMOLAR

Annotasiya: *Mamlakatimizda hozirgi kunda til o'rganishga bo'lgan e'tibor kundan kunga ortib bormoqda . Xususan maktabgacha ta'lim , maktab , oliy hamda o'rta maxsus ta'lim muassasalarida bir qancha xorijiy tillar fan sifatida o'rgatilib kelinmoqda . Bu jarayonda o'qitish bilan ko'plab muammolar yuzaga keladi . Ayniqsa maktabda yosh til o'rganuvchi o'quvchilar orasida qator bu kabi muammolarni uchratish mumkin. Ushbu maqolada maktab yoshidagi bolalar til o'rganish mobaynida aynan reading o'qitishdagi ayrim kamchiliklar va ularning yechimlari borasida fikr yuritilgan .*

Kalit so'zlar: *Fonetik qiyinchiliklar , visual yordamlar , o'qitish malakasi , grammatik tuzilmalar.*

ПРОБЛЕМЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ЧТЕНИЮ ДЕТЕЙ ШКОЛЬНОГО ВОЗРАСТА

Аннотация: *В нашей стране внимание к изучению языков возрастает с каждым днем. В частности, ряд иностранных языков преподается как предмет в дошкольных, школьных, высших и средних специальных учебных заведениях. В этом процессе возникает много проблем с преподаванием. С рядом таких проблем можно столкнуться, особенно среди молодых людей, изучающих язык в школе. В данной статье рассматриваются некоторые недостатки обучения чтению детей школьного возраста в процессе изучения языка и пути их решения.*

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Ключевые слова: фонетические трудности, наглядные пособия, педагогические навыки, грамматические конструкции.

School age to the children study to teach in the process one row problems appear to be can Some children book to study natural interest have it won't be . They pay attention long term save can't or study they consider it boring . Reading qualification low Reading qualifications in development children some sounds separate the letters recognize get and them right in application to difficulties face coming can of this process complexity in study to slow down take will come Reading of learning important part the text is understanding . Children read text content right if they don't understand , that's it their interest reduces and study process it becomes difficult . At home parents or big of ages to study attention does not give or lack of support of children to study has been ability restriction can House conditions to study attention enough if not , children fail at school too meeting can Every child to study different at speed learns To some more time and addition exercises need to be can But the teacher or parents this in consideration if not , the child himself behind feels like staying and this of trust to decrease take will come School age English language studying teaching children to read to himself special problems there is . Children in this mother from the language different the language studying that it was for special approach and addition help is required .

Main problems :

- Phonetic difficulties
- Word of wealth lack of
- Cultural differences
- Reading speed and pronunciation difficulties
- Of interest lack of
- Supporting environment lack of

English of the language pronunciation and spelling to each other suitable does not come (for example , a different sounds different different in words written) children distraction can This is especially the mother in the language phonetic and graphematic compatibility strong has been children for problem gives birth English language learning children most of the time limited word wealth have will be And this study in the process to understand because it makes it difficult they are in the text many stranger to words face they come Grammatical structures complexity : English in the

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language grammar structures some children for complicated to be can He is studying of the text content right to understand for grammar the rules to know and them apply get important In the texts cultural features and contexts children for you don't understand to be can Some words or expressions their diary in his life is not used or in general cultural in terms of familiar it's not . English in the language is studying children most of the time the words right pronunciation in doing to difficulties face they come Not only that the text to understand , maybe common respectively study speed is also affected does To understand development difficulties : Words study learning one thing , but of the text content complete to understand another thing English in the language texts stranger words and expressions because of children for complicated to be it is possible while common to understand makes it difficult . Some children English in the language text to study lack of interest because it is possible this to them complicated and difficult it seems In this case of motivation decrease is also observed . House conditions English in the language study for chance or resources lack of of children English in the language texts study qualifications development hindrance to do can Bringing passed to problems one row methods using eliminate reach can Phonetic study methods application , Letters and sounds between dependence better explainer phonetic exercises with to the children help to give can Texts simple and to the children Adaptation : Texts of the child word wealth Adaptation is understandable and interesting stories with motivation increase Visual aids , Pictures and diagrams through text content to understand help to give To the context based on teaching : To children stranger the words in context explanation and cultural aspects explain study process makes it easier . Parents and teachers with cooperation : At home and at school addition help show , more study opportunities create through to the children help to give These are the methods using of children English in the language texts to understand ability develops and in study difficulties to overcome help gives

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